

PRACTICAL, GENERAL EDUCATIONAL, EDUCATIONAL AND DEVELOPMENTAL PURPOSE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**Eshmakhtova Farangiz**Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute, 1st year student of foreign language and literature<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6808201>

Abstract. This article covers the various objectives of foreign language teaching. It is known that learning or teaching foreign languages is very different from our mother tongue in some aspects. This requires the purpose of teaching a foreign language and the use of foreign language technology. In a time when the world is growing rapidly, knowledge of languages, especially polyglossia, is gaining great importance.

The goals of foreign language education have been widely discussed in methodological literature.

Key words: polyglossia, association, innovative, foreign language, authentic, tactic, strategy, plan, abstract, methodology, term, motivational, emotion.

ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ, ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНАЯ, ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНАЯ И РАЗВИВАЮЩАЯ ЦЕЛЬ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматриваются различные цели обучения иностранному языку. Известно, что изучение или преподавание иностранных языков в некоторых аспектах сильно отличается от нашего родного языка. Для этого необходима цель обучения иностранному языку и использование иноязычных технологий. В наше время, когда мир стремительно развивается, большое значение приобретает знание языков, особенно многоязычия.

Цели иноязычного образования широко обсуждаются в методической литературе.

Ключевые слова: многоязычие, ассоциация, инновационный, иностранный язык, аутентичный, тактика, стратегия, план, реферат, методология, термин, мотивация, эмоция.

INTRODUCTION

Any goal arises because of needs. The concept of a goal means a planned result, an imagined consequence. Educational goals are a social order-task, focused on the formation and education of a comprehensively developed person.

Foreign language learners come into contact with a different language and a different culture in foreign language education. For this reason, authentic materials specific to that foreign language and that culture should be used in the training sessions. It is recommended to use texts and literature that can deliver.

Successful foreign language learning requires comprehensive methods. The quantity and quality of exposure to communication are the main reasons for faster language learning. In addition, the successful learning of foreign languages depends on whether there is an opportunity to apply what has been learned.

In foreign language education, first of all, it should be encouraged to learn everyday, real knowledge and skills in a foreign language, but the development of specific knowledge should not be neglected.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The current educational development creates a new direction of innovative pedagogy. So, the main goals of foreign language teaching are as follows:

practical purpose

general educational purpose

educational purpose

developer goal

The practical purpose of teaching a foreign language: the term "PRACTICAL" methodology has caused more than one association among teachers and evokes different forms of understanding. There is also a correct general definition of the practical acquisition of a foreign language as understanding the speech of others and expressing one's own opinion. The ultimate goal of learning a foreign language in a practical way in a secondary education course is to get information by reading. Graduates of schools, lyceums and colleges, with the ultimate goal of learning a speech activity in a foreign language.

The intermediate goal is different, and speaking can be taught as an intermediate goal in the classroom or in individual classes.

Understanding the learning objective—helps to know the general strategy of teaching. The goal is realized by completing many specific tasks during the lesson and independent work.

Solving tasks is a teaching tactic. Educational tasks consist of practical tasks performed by students (understanding, expressing opinions, etc.)

General educational goal of foreign language teaching: Students are taught a foreign language as a third language. Both the result and the process of learning a foreign language are of general educational importance. Because in addition to the information obtained through the medium of a foreign language, language units used in the process of learning it develop thinking, new events in the expression plan of speech are interesting for students and enrich their language experience. Pupils will be familiar with the culture, art, history, literature, customs and traditions of the countries where the language is being studied. They enjoy a cumulative function as a treasure of folk culture. Studying a foreign language for educational purposes is beneficial for developing the student's logical thinking, improving memory, and raising the general culture of their knowledge level. By learning a foreign language, students learn language phenomena as real facts in speech. By learning a foreign language at the level of speech communication, the student will understand its content plan on the basis of language tools. So, the object of general education is three: language phenomenon, concept and rules and content of speech. They have specific sizes and dimensions.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Conducting speech activity, as a result, exchanging information, is the only multifaceted goal of teaching a foreign language. But the material used in the speech itself is the knowledge that becomes a skill, and the abstract knowledge that is formed from it is in the series of simple rules.

In a word, the rules are knowledge of language units and text content, general education in a foreign language.

General education is realized during the practical knowledge of a foreign language. Practical knowledge is also the main way to educate.

The educational purpose of teaching a foreign language : as we all know, the importance of education and training has existed since ancient times. The education system, of course, focuses on education, the concept of education or being educated cannot be imagined without education. In English, the single word "EDUCATION" means education and upbringing. The educational goal of teaching a foreign language is briefly described in the methodological science: to give students ideological and political education, to develop intellectual work skills and competencies in them, and to increase the activity of knowing students. The educational goal is mainly realized in two different ways. First: students are directly educated in the process of learning a foreign

language. The second methodical method of implementing the educational goal in foreign language teaching is the educational use of this language material.

There are many passages or texts in textbooks and teaching books that provide ideological and political education. The content of texts about great thinkers, scientists, poets shows positive results in educating students.

Various studies on the types of education show that a foreign language is an important factor in this aspect.

: the developmental goal is a newly accepted scientific category in the methodology of foreign language teaching. The name of this goal was created by imitation on the basis of the concept "RIVIJLANTIRUVCHU METOD" which is well-known in linguistics. There is no such method in language teaching, but in the name of the **developmental goal** of foreign language teaching, this term was introduced into the scientific-methodical circulation.

The concept of "developmental purpose" begins to express the development of the intellectual, emotional and motivational side of the student's personality. Psychologists and educationalists agree that if students are taught to overcome enough difficulties in the educational process, their thinking can be developed quickly. The maturity of a person is connected not only with the development of thinking, but also with the development of his inner feelings.

It is possible to realize the internal experiences (emotions) and internal motivation (motivation) of the student in foreign language methodology. As a result, the motivation to learn a foreign language increases.

A developmental goal is revealed only through speech acts. Education is considered a component of development.

CONCLUSION

The practical purpose of learning a foreign language is to learn to communicate in a foreign language; Educational goal - ideological and political education; formation of mental labor skills; increasing students' cognitive activity; Educational goal - development of memory and logical thinking; improvement of students' level of knowledge and general culture; Developmental goal- includes the development of both mental and spiritual qualities of the student. The world does not stop growing and developing, so people should not stop learning and exploring.

References

1. English language teaching methodology G.T.Mahkamov, J.J.Jalolov, Sh.S.Ashurov
2. Foreign language teaching methodology. J.Jalolov.
3. Ibrohimjon, M. (2022). PSYCHOLOGICAL CRISES IN PERSONALITY PSYCHOLOGY AND WAYS TO OVERCOME THEM. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 743-746.